

Always-On Learning: Shaping Robot Cognition Through First-Hand Experience¹

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Figure 1: (left) the cognitive architecture; the consolidated long-term memory in our Office (center) and at Humanoids 2024 (right).

I. MOTIVATION

Understanding and adapting to a dynamic environment is crucial for autonomous robots operating in real-world settings. Our ambition is to develop a robot that autonomously learns from experience and determines how to act in its environment. Beyond perceiving and acting, the robot must identify what information and actions matter most—developing a personal value system—while efficiently memorizing, recalling, and selectively forgetting. This enables it to recognize patterns, understand its experiences, and anticipate the consequences of its own and others' actions—forming a personalized, situated, and embodied Artificial Cognition (ACo) [1]. Traditional task-oriented models trained on vast datasets fall short. Instead, the robot must be **Always-On**, continuously interacting with its surroundings. To support this, we propose a cognitive architecture that enables ongoing perception, value-driven integration, and memory formation. Prioritizing emergence and first-hand interaction, we adopt an enactive, developmental-inspired approach, incrementally integrating cognitive components for multimodal learning.

II. ARCHITECTURE

Our preliminary architecture (Figure 1, left) enables active observation, a fundamental aspect of human development [2], allowing the robot to identify patterns from raw sensory input, supporting emergent cognition. We embodied it in the ICubHead, a 6-DoF actuated head mounted on a stationary 3D-printed upper body equipped with cameras, a stereo microphone, a speaker, and expressive LEDs. The architecture consists of 4 modules: The **Multimodal Perception** processes real-time RGB images (640x480, 30 fps) and audio (44.1 kHz), extracting five core features inspired by early human development: *number of faces*, *mutual gaze*, *motion*, *illumination*, and *stereo RMS audio levels*. The **Embodied Behavior** directs the ICubHead, alternating between static and gaze-wandering phases to seek and track human faces, mirroring infants' social drive [3]. The **Episode Segmentation** synchronizes perceptual data, joint states, and behavior into timestamped *Event* objects, segmenting them into *Episodes* based on novelty detection. Events deviating by more than three standard deviations from the mean of the 5 core features trigger a new episode. Lastly, the **Episodic Memory** stores event-related core features, episodic statistics, and raw images and audio paths in an SQLite database. Pretrained SlowFast (images) and VGGish (audio) models embed raw episodes data (528-long vector) for efficient comparison. Such embeddings

are daily integrated into Long-Term Memory through a continuous **memory consolidation** process. The architecture reduces the 528-dimensional episode embeddings to a 2D space using UMAP, then clusters them with HDBSCAN. These evolving models classify new episodes in real time, distinguishing between *familiar* experiences – where the robot should act consistently – and *novel* ones, which require increased attention to refine its understanding of the environment.

III. VALIDATION²

We validated the architecture over 15 days: 4 in our office, 4 at ICRA@40, 4 at ECCV 2024, and 3 at Humanoids 2024. Here, we focus on the office and Humanoids results. In the office, the ICubHead observed a break area, recording 449 episodes ($M=112$, $SD=83$), 90% between 1–2 PM, aligning with lunch breaks. These episodes were shorter (avg. 1 min vs. 25 min otherwise) due to increased activity, leading to greater perception variability and more frequent segmentation. Long-term memory revealed four main clusters (*silhouette*=0.65, Figure 1 center): **lively** episodes (0, blue) with the most faces ($B=1.77$, $t=17.72$, $p<0.001$) and highest audio RMS ($B=6.86$, $t=11.59$, $p<0.001$); and **calm** episodes with the highest illumination (1, yellow, $B=0.15$, $t=7.48$, $p<0.001$) or least motion (3, green, $B=-0.44$, $t=5.61$, $p<0.001$). At Humanoids 2024, the robot recorded 2304 episodes ($M=768$, $SD=270$). Memory clustering (*silhouette*=0.25, Figure 1 right) replicated the office results, identifying **lively** episodes (0, blue) with more faces ($B=0.94$, $t=1.41$, $p<0.001$), motion, mutual gaze, and audio, and **calm** episodes (1, orange) with lower activity. Notably, 65% of lively episodes occurred between 2–4 PM, coinciding with coffee breaks, while 87% of calm episodes aligned with talk sessions. In just a few days, our architecture autonomously learned to distinguish lively from calm moments, demonstrating its ability to generalize across two radically different environments. This knowledge is key to enabling proactive behavior—seeking interactions during lively periods and focusing on memory consolidation during calm ones.

REFERENCES

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